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HARDINESS AS ATTITUDE AND COPING OF PERSON'S SELF-DEVELOPMENT

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Actuality: the phenomenon of hardiness of the modern man in particular in different age groups has been reviewed in the article; the problem of the problem of connection of the general level of hardiness and level of actualization of self-development personality resources has been analyzed. The relevance of the study has been caused by the need to determine the adaptive capacity of people to rapidly changing conditions of modern reality. It has been indicated that the results of the study will determine the correlation between the indicators of hardiness and self-development.

Aim: check the hypothesis of different levels of hardiness at the representatives of different generations and professional direction. *Materials:* 137 respondents aged 18 to 55 have been taken part in the study; they are future specialists in practical psychology, international relations, civil protection, health system specialists.

Results: a difference in the indicators of hardiness and its structural components in the following groups of respondents using statistical data processing methods, using the computer program SPSS Statistics 17.0 have been found. It has been shown that the severity of hardiness on average does not depend on education and age, but the difference between the manifestations of its components has been revealed. It has been shown that the level of hardiness of young people has its own peculiarities: the components have dynamic manifestations both higher and lower than standard ones.

Keywords: hardiness; self development; involvement; control; taking risk.

Життєстійкість як настанова і копінг саморозвитку особистості

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Актуальність: в статті розглядається феномен життєстійкості сучасної людини, зокрема у різних вікових групах; аналізується проблема зв'язку загального рівня життєстійкості тарівня актуалізації ресурсів саморозвитку особистості. Актуальність дослідження обумовлена необхідністю визначення адаптаційних можливостей людей до швидко змінних умов сучасної дійсності.

Вказується, що результати дослідження дозволять визначити кореляційні зв'язки показників життєстійкості і саморозвитку.

Мета: перевірити гіпотезу про різний рівень життєстійкості у представників різних поколінь та професійного спрямування. Матеріали: в дослідженні прийняли участь 137 респондентів віком від 18 до 55 років, які є майбутніми фахівцями в галузі практичної психології, міжнародних відносин, цивільного захисту, а також працюючими фахівцями системи охорони здоров'я.

Результати: за допомогою методів статистичної обробки даних, з використанням комп'ютерної програми SPSS Statistics 17.0, виявлено різницю в показниках життєстійкості і її структурних компонентів у наведених групах респондентів. Показано, що вираженість життєстійкості в середньому не залежить від освіти та віку, але виявлено різницю між проявами її компонентів. Показано, що рівень життєстійкості у молоді має свої особливості: компоненти мають динамічні прояви як вище, так і нижче нормативних.

***Ключові слова:** життєстійкість; саморозвиток; залученість; контроль; прийняття ризику.*

Introduction. The necessity of studying the psychological components of the phenomenon of «hardiness» is due to the insufficient study of the socio-psychological mechanisms of life-sustaining behavior, which forms the basis of qualitative and self-efficacious life activities. On the other hand it is due to the lack of modern research of the coherency of the phenomenon of "hardiness" with personal self-development.

Although these phenomena are complex, the peculiarities of self-realization of people are not sufficiently taken into account, in particular, the individual picture of hardiness in comparison with actualization of a certain resource of self-development has not been studied.

For the first time, the phenomenon of «hardiness» appears in the scientific literature in the 80 years of the twentieth century thanks to S. Maddi and S. Cobies. In foreign sources, viability is denoted as "hardiness", which translates from English as «endurance», «stability». From the author's point of view, this phenomenon allows the individual to recognize real possibilities and to accept its own vulnerability (Nalivajko, 2006). Within the resource approach, S. Maddi defines «hardiness» as an integral personal trait that is responsible for the success of overcoming the personality of life's difficulties, which allows maintaining internal balance and harmony (Aleksandrova, 2005). S. Maddi and D. Koshaba have been developed a psychometrically adequate method for measuring the phenomenon of «hardiness», and studied the conjunction between this method and the scale of the MMPI (Minnesota Multi-factor Personal Questionnaire). The results of this research have shown that the considered phenomenon is a general measure of mental health and can be used in the context of the research of problem of coping with stress. Considering

«hardiness» as a personal quality, researchers emphasized the importance of attitudes that motivate people to transform stressful life events (Rubinshtejn, 1973). Individual attitude to change, the ability to use its own internal resources, that help to manage stressful situations effectively, determine the ability of a person to coping with arising difficulties. Thus, we can say that «hardiness» is a solid element of guidance and skills that allows transform unstable situations of changes into positive opportunities.

However, it is important to understand that this phenomenon is not identical to the coping strategies that were considered by R. Lazarus and S. Folkman. From their point of view, these strategies are aimed at overcoming difficult life situations in such a way that the person uses a strategy: confrontation, distance, self-control, social support, responsibility, avoidance, planned problem solving and reevaluation (*Lazarus, 1973*). That is, coping strategies represented as a certain algorithm, a system of actions that are traditional for person and can lead not only to the reproduction of productive behavior, but also to regression, while «hardiness» is a guide to survival, a personal trait that mobilizes internal forces of the person, activates creativity and allows to cope with stress effectively in the direction of personal growth.

In domestic psychology D. O. Leontiev was dealt with the adaptation of the concept of «hardiness», calling this phenomenon a «hardiness», therefore in further research we consider it expedient to denote this phenomenon exactly this way. D. O. Leontiev and O. I. Rasskazova in the context of the existential approach to the study of personality indicate that hardiness is understood as a system of human beliefs about himself, the world, relations with the world. On the one hand, resilient beliefs affect the assessment of the situation due to readiness to act actively and confidence in the ability to influence the situation; it is perceived as less traumatic. On the other hand, hardiness contributes to the active overcoming of difficulties. It stimulates the care of its own health and well-being, due to which stress, which is perceived by man, does not grow into chronic and does not lead to psychosomatic illnesses (Nalivajko, 2006). Therefore, it is quite logical to assume that the hardiness is associated with tolerance to the uncertainty associated with the construct of its own action. According to D. O. Leontiev, the main component of hardiness is a person's conviction in being prepared to deal with the situation and openness to everything new. Hardiness affects both the assessment of the actual situation, which is perceived as less traumatic, so the subsequent actions of the person, stimulating to care for health and psychological well-being.

Aim is to present the obtained data of the empirical study of the

peculiarities and components of hardiness, to substantiate their correlation with psychological resources of personal self-development.

Methodology of Research. There were used such method to hold the empirical research: the method «Personal readiness for change» (authors: Rodnik, Heather, Gold, Hal; adaptation: N. A. Bazhanova, G. L. Bardier), questionnaire «Tolerance to uncertainty» (author: C. Badner, adaptation: G. U. Soldatova), the test «Hardiness» (author S. Muddy, adaptation: D. O. Leontiev, O. I. Rasskazova), the method «Disposition characteristic of personal self-development» (author: S. B. Kuzikova). The research is based on a sample of 137 youth and adolescents. The sample consists of the future specialists in the field of practical psychology, international relations, civil protection, as well as working professionals in the health care system. Methods of mathematical and statistical data processing: single-factor dispersion analysis, Pearson correlation analysis. Data have been obtained in SPSS Statistics 17.0.

Results. According to researchers, the general idea of hardiness is the effective use of human psychological capabilities in difficult life situations, that is, its «psychological vitality» and «expanded efficiency». Various factors of the environment, individual peculiarities of the psyche, specificity of interaction with the world can both promote and prevent the development and manifestation of hardiness as integral personal quality. The problem of development, the peculiarities of manifestation of this necessary integral personal quality in modern science remains poorly studied, despite the profound understanding of the phenomenon of hardiness in scientific works. In the first phase of our study, we examined the assumption that tolerance to uncertainty is a factor of individual hardiness, which is presented as a process that helps to «cope» with negative situations. We applied a one-factor dispersion analysis to identify the effect and test the hypothesis of tolerance to uncertainty as the factor of a person's hardiness. Due to the analysis of the mean values corresponding to different gradations of the factor and their differences, the one-factor dispersion analysis allows us to verify the hypothesis that the investigated factor influences the dependent variable and how it occurs.

Below are the most significant results of the analysis, where the level of tolerance to uncertainty serves as a factor (independent variable). Obtained results indicate that the construct of tolerance to uncertainty affects the following scales: passion ($F=2,053$ при $p=0,033$), optimism ($F=2,332$ при $p=0,015$), need for self-development ($F=4,477$ при $p=0,000$). Other scales were excluded from the single-factor dispersion analysis, as the results were $p > 0.05$. The obtained results allowed us to establish that tolerance to uncertainty is a complex construct that determines the processes of person's

self-development, and also influences the level of person's passion and optimism.

Table 1

Results of a single-factor dispersion analysis

		Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Medium square	F	Value
Passion	Between groups	435,667	15	29,044	,053	033
	Inside the group	622,333	44	14,144		
	Total	1058,000	59			
Optimism	Between groups	463,661	15	30,911	,332	015
	Inside the group	583,322	44	13,257		
	Total	1046,983	59			
Need	Between groups	949,711	15	63,314	,643	000
	Inside the group	764,689	44	17,379		
	Total	1714,400	59			
Overall rate of a self-development	Between groups	3898,311	15	259,887	4,477	,000
	Inside the group	2554,089	44	58,047		
	Total	6452,400	59			

The impact of tolerance to uncertainty on the component of the person's hardiness is not straightforward, but is realized indirectly with the help of other variables, namely the general indicator and the need for self-development (Kuzikova, 2017). The high average and high level of tolerance to uncertainty is a characteristic of an independent person with developed semantic life orientations. Factors of the development of such a person are the general (not only situational) active orientation to activity, faith in oneself, in the proper future, the functioning of the higher system of regulation of activity, strategic orientation and the absence of impulsive behavior. An individual who strives for self-development, skillfully

withstands stressful situations, maintains an internal balance and does not lose the productivity of the activity he performs (Kuzikova, 2015). Positive attitude to own changes, internal resources and opportunities to adequately assess the ability to manage these changes and the difficulties that arise in the way of their formation, can determine the person's potential to overcome these difficulties in everyday life, even if they are complex.

Test «Hardiness», used to measure the overall person's hardiness and to study the level of its components; contains four scales, the analysis of which is presented below.

1. Involvement. Involvement was first used by social psychologists to characterize the adaptation of the individual to its role. It is defined as «certainty that engagement in what's happening gives you the maximum chance to find something worthy and interesting for an individual». A person with a developed component of involvement receives a pleasure from activities, in the process of which he is experiencing its significance, value. Involvement is also defined as the physical, emotional and intellectual state that motivates a person to perform work as best as possible. The following results were obtained: cadets (future specialists in the field of civil protection) – 25% high level, 50% – average level, 25% – low; participants of the program «Work & Travel» (future specialists in the field of international relations) – 80% average level, 20% – low level; students–future psychologists – 70% average level, 30% – low level; mature persons (working health care professionals) – 40% high level, 60% – average level. The results of all samples obtained average values. Conducted pair correlations in the statistical analysis showed that the indicator of «involvement» statistically positively significantly correlates with the indicator «self-development» ($r=0,647$) «general level of self-development» ($r=0,457$). Correlation is at 0,01 level and is bilateral (0,000). Since involvement in our research is characterized by self-confidence and self-capabilities, this indicator has a clear connection with the component of «confidence» as presented above. Involvement is a condition for achieving high goals and prevents stagnation, promotes the mobilization of energy and creativity, which is aimed not only at activities but also at internal processes.

2. Control. Control is the belief that the struggle allows you to influence the outcome of what is happening, even if this influence is not absolute and success is not guaranteed. The opposite of this is the feeling of helplessness. A person with a strongly developed component of control feels that he chooses his own activities, his own way. The component of control is similar to J. Rotter's category of «control locus», which is the person's propensity to attribute responsibility for life events and the results

of self activities to external forces (externality, external locus of control) or to their own abilities and efforts (internality, internal control locus). The following results were obtained: students – 30% high level, 70% – average level; participants of the program «Work & Travel» – 20% high level, 80% average level; students-psychologists – 80% average level, 20% – low level; mature persons – 30% high level, 60% – average level, 10% – low level. The analyzed pair correlations in the statistical analysis showed that the indicator «control» statistically significantly positively correlates with the indicator «self-development» ($r=0,460$) and «optimism» ($r=0,467$) at the level of tendency. Correlation is at 0,01 level and is bilateral (0,000). Obtained data are the basis for a possible further study of the relationship between the given indicators. Optimism can be the result of long and effective work on oneself; this is person's confidence in the fact that, regardless of the difficulties that have to be solved, it will succeed. Thus, the person controls everything that happens, including self-development (Kuzikova, 2015).

3. Risk taking. Risk taking is a person's conviction that all that happens to her contributes to development at the expense of experience is not important, positive or negative. A person who views life as a way of gaining experience is ready to act in the absence of reliable guarantees of success at own risk, believing that the desire for simple comfort and safety impoverishes life. The basis of risk acceptance is the idea of development through the active assimilation of knowledge from experience and the use of them next time. This component allows remain open to the surrounding world and perceive occurring events as a challenge and test. The following results were obtained: students – 60% high level, 25% – average level, 15% – low level; participants of the program «Work & Travel» – 100% high level; students-psychologists – 40% high level, 60% - average level; persons of mature age – 30% high level, 70% – average level. Participants of the program «Work & Travel» have absolutely high level of risk-taking, it may be due to their preparation in agencies that organize this program. Young people analyze possible risk situations to be prepared for various surprises and overcome them.

4. Overall scale of hardiness. Hardiness is a system of beliefs about oneself, about the world, about the attitude to the world. This is a disposition that includes three relatively autonomous components: involvement, control, risk taking; analysis of these results are presented above. The expressiveness of these components of hardiness in general prevents the emergence of internal stress in stress situations due to the rapid use of coping strategies in order to cope with stress and perceive them as

less significant impacts. The following results were obtained: cadets – 40% high level, 50% – average level, 10% – low level; participants of the program «Work & Travel» – 40% high level, 60% average level; students-psychologists – 80% average level, 10% – low level; persons of mature age – 40% high level, 60% – average level. Respondents of all four samples have approximately the same level of hardiness. According to the average rates, it was found that the results are average and roughly equally distributed over the levels.

The method used in the research «Disposition characteristic of personal self-development» contains four scales. The results of significant correlations are presented below. Self-development of personality is considered as a progressive, conscious and self-directed process of personality changes and growth. The need for self-development as its source and determinant; conditions that ensure its success; mechanisms as functional means of its implementation are defined as psychological resources of self-development (structural components of a holistic system of personal self-development) (Kuzikova, 2017). The feedback between the indicators of «ambiguity» and the «Overall self-development» ($r = 0,460$) was determined in the correlation analysis; the correlation is one-way. This is evidence of the fact that situations of ambiguity, uncertainty are not critical to a person who seeks self-development and has high indicators of this integral characteristic.

The need for self-development is determined by the actualization of the characteristics of self-development (self-activity, vital functions, development of self-awareness). It is provided by the basic level of personal self-development (the area of actual development), as well as the saturation of the person's life (the zone of the immediate development) and arises when the content structure of the individual consciousness changes and the transformation of semantic entities takes place. Correlation analysis showed that there is a stable correlation between the indicators of «optimism» and «need for self-development». Bilateral correlation at the level of 0,01 ($r=0,546$). Belief in success, reluctance to focus on the worse development of events, fixation not on problems, but on the opportunities that they provide for personal growth, increase the need for self-development, the desire for it and vice versa.

The psychological conditions that ensure the success of self-development are: mature person's «self» (it is such characteristics as autonomy, self-identity, internality), openness, tolerance to the new, the presence of a conscious goal of self-realization as a guide to self-development (Kuzikova, 2017). During the correlation analysis, a significant correlation was found at the level of 0,01 between the indicators

of «passion» and «conditions of self-development» ($r=0,460$); it is bilateral. According to these data, we can say that with high fervor and activity, the personality is capable of creating productive conditions for development. Mechanisms as a means of self-development are reflection, self-regulation and feedback. No additional significant correlations were found.

Discussion. We share the opinion of L. A. Aleksandrova, who indicates that hardiness as a special integral ability that promotes successful adaptation of the person (Aleksandrova). Its main components are systematized into two blocks: block of general abilities, which includes basic personal guides, intelligence, self-awareness, meaning and responsibility; a block of special abilities that includes human interaction skills as well as skills to overcome various types of difficult situations. Researches of L. A. Alexandrova showed that a high level of hardiness contributes to successful personal adaptation, and also prevents increasing of anxiety and the emergence of stress in the adaptation period. It has also been established that hardiness is negatively associated with depression, using non-adaptive coping mechanisms, as well as some symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (Merenluoto, Lehtinen, 2004).

Hardiness is developed and transformed in the process of human life, based on its positive attitude towards itself and a sense of satisfaction from one's own life, which includes values-semantic guides to their own ability to determine and control the events of their lives. Hardiness is mediated by factors such as typological features, age, occupation, social status, and manifested in the features of conscious self-regulation, the success of overcoming stressful situations, the implementation of the life program. Hardiness is connected not only with behavior, but also with various means of realization of everyday life and possible moments of vital uncertainty.

Summarizing the results of the research of D. A. Leontiev, O. I. Rasskazova (2006), T. V. Nalyvayko (2006), S. L. Rubinstein (1973), we can distinguish three main directions of study of hardiness:

1) Direct correlation between somatic and psychological health. In the conducted researches, individuals with a low level of anxiety and a high level of hardiness showed an almost imperceptible physiological response of the body to emerging stress.

2) Interrelation with social and behavioral components. Hardiness acts on resources of overcoming stress through increasing self-efficacy and self-development. People with high level of hardiness feel competent, have higher cognitive assessments, developed coping strategies, and generally experience a significantly lower level of stress in their everyday lives.

3) The meaning of semantic structures. In the conducted researches, it

was found that people with a low level of hardiness has mostly memories of those situations in which they appeared not in the winning position, felt helpless and could not manage. Respondents with a high level of hardiness showed a reverse tendency, as they mentioned positive situations, which successfully managed the emerging circumstances.

Thus, the phenomenon of hardiness is an inalienable personality formation that develops in person's life. It means a dedicated significant property of the human psyche, a multicomponent entity that influences on the actualization of other features of the human psyche in situations of vital stress. The study confirms two leading thoughts: the focus of professional interests really imposes on a person a certain responsibility, according to which it should exhibit hardiness in certain situations of uncertainty; components of hardiness are implemented indirectly using a common indicator and the need for self-development. The high average and high level of hardiness are characteristic of an independent person with developed semantic life orientations, which is also detailed in the studies V. I. Morasanova (2010).

Conclusions. Thus, in our study it has been established that hardiness is the internal component that every person can develop. This is a quality that can be transformed, it can support not only physical but also mental and social health. The study of the phenomenon of hardiness in foreign and domestic scientific sources suggests that the contradictions in the considered interpretations show not the diversity of approaches, but the specificity of the levels of analysis of the problem: from adaptation to person's self-determination. The generalized scientific material has been revealed the correlation between this phenomenon and socio-cultural environment as a factor affecting the development of the integral characteristics of individual. Among the highlighted in the research opinions, two have been confirmed: the orientation of professional interests really imposes certain responsibility, therefore, the person should be ready for uncertain situations and have a thorough vocational training; the impact of tolerance to uncertainty on the components of the person's hardiness is not straightforward, but is realized indirectly with the help of other variables, namely the general indicator and the need for self-development. Thus, the phenomenon of hardiness is directly related to the process of individual self-development.

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